

JMM profile: Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP): for the rapid detection of nucleic acid targets in resource-limited settings

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Graphical abstract

Schematic illustration of loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) applications, targets and possible detection signals. (a) LAMP is used for pathogen and/or antimicrobial resistance detection in pen-side/veterinary medicine or medical settings (bedside). Pen-side diagnostics refers to tests that are able to provide rapid and real-time information on the farm/in practice. (b) LAMP can detect the nucleic acid of parasites, bacteria, fungi, viruses, etc. (c) The most commonly used detection signals are either colorimetric or fluorescent, but they can also be combined with lateral flow or mobile phone detection systems. The figure was created by M.M.H. using Biorender.com in March 2021 and edited in November 2021.

Abstract

Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) is a rapid alternative to PCR, in which the reaction occurs at one temperature and uses a polymerase with high displacement activity, e.g. *Bacillus stearothermophilus* DNA polymerase I (*Bst*) or homologues. Since the discovery of LAMP in 2000, several applications have been developed to employ this technique in the rapid detection of nucleic acid targets and enhance its performance. Improvements to the LAMP technique and a variety of innovative detection methods have led to its application for a wide range of targets in medical and veterinary microbiology, particularly in resource-poor settings. The key advantages of LAMP-based diagnostics include the ability to rapidly detect target nucleic acid sequences within 30 min and its ease of use, facilitating its application in field, bedside, pen-side, point-of-care and point-of-need diagnostic settings. LAMP can be a valuable tool to aid in the detection and management of disease outbreaks.

HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

The LAMP technique was originally developed in 2000 by Notomi *et al.* [1] as a novel, rapid DNA or RNA (with reverse transcriptase) amplification method. To demonstrate the various properties of LAMP and to optimize conditions of the assay, three targets were used: M13mp18, the double-stranded, covalently closed circular form of DNA derived from bacteriophage M13; hepatitis B virus (HBV), which has a partially double-stranded circular DNA genome; and prostate-specific antigen messenger RNA. Using M13, a target size range of 130–200 bp was found to provide the best results. Therefore, it was suggested that an optimal target size of <300 bp DNA should be used. The sensitivity of the LAMP assay was also demonstrated, with as few as six copies of HBV DNA being detected. Further publications have focused on how turbidity could be used for the detection of LAMP reactions [2].

HOW THE DIAGNOSTIC TEST WORKS

LAMP is performed at an isothermal constant temperature, most commonly at 65 °C, where LAMP primers (two or three primer pairs) bind to the target DNA sequence to start amplification and strand displacement steps. The two initial primer pairs are the forward and reverse inner primers (FIP and BIP) and the forward and reverse external primers (F3 and B3), respectively (Fig. 1a). The third primer pair comprises the forward and reverse loop primers (LF and LB) (Fig. 1a), which are often used to enhance the speed and specificity of the assay. The target amplification starts by the binding of one of the inner primers (FIP) to the target sequence (in blue), polymerizing the complementary strand (in grey) (Fig. 1b). The upstream outer primer (F3) then initiates strand amplification (Fig. 1d, in light blue), displacing the newly formed strand (in grey) and forming the first loop structure on one of the strand ends (3' end) (Fig. 1c). The same process occurs on the other strand end, leading to the formation of the LAMP dumbbell structure (Fig. 1d) [1, 3]. The LAMP dumbbell structure and other formed strands contain multiple amplification initiation sites, allowing for a rapid chain reaction of isothermal amplification [1]. The increase in amplified target dsDNA can be detected turbidimetrically due to the generation of magnesium pyrophosphate [2], fluorescently by dsDNA-specific dyes such as SYBR green, or calcein or colorimetrically through pH change using a pH-sensitive dye such as phenol red or neutral red [4].

GUIDELINES

To design a LAMP assay the nucleic acid target (DNA or RNA) region must first be defined, then the LAMP assay type (single-plex or multiplex) and a suitable detection signal (turbidimetric, colorimetric, fluorescent or lateral flow detection) are selected.

Generally, LAMP requires a minimum of two sets of primers, the internal (FIP, BIP) and external (F3, B3); however, the addition of a third set of loop primers (LF, LB) can increase the assay performance, resulting in three sets of primers for each LAMP target. The design of these primers is governed by general melting temperatures, distances between primers, stability, formation of secondary structures and GC content rules. LAMP assay primers can be designed using a variety of software, e.g. LAMP

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Abbreviations: AMR, antimicrobial resistance; B3, reverse external primer; BIP, reverse inner primer; F3, forward external primer; FIP, forward inner primer; LAMP, loop-mediated isothermal amplification; LB, reverse loop primer; LEC-LAMP, loop-primer endonuclease cleavage LAMP; LF, forward loop primer; MERT-LAMP, multiple endonuclease restriction real-time LAMP; SARS-CoV-2, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2.

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Fig. 1. Schematic illustration showing the binding sites for LAMP primers and how the assay works. The figure was created by M.M.H. using Microsoft PowerPoint for Office 365 in March 2021 and edited in November 2021.

designer software (Optigene) or web-based tools such as PrimerExplorer (Eiken Chemical Co. Ltd). It should be noted that the use of the lateral flow format for amplicon detection requires primer modification to allow the immobilization of the amplified target sequences on the lateral flow device.

Types of LAMP assays and platforms

1. Single target LAMP

- (i) LAMP (DNA target) is the regular LAMP assay that has been used to detect a wide range of pathogens using *Bst* DNA polymerase, a strand displacing DNA polymerase enzyme [4].
- (ii) RT-LAMP (RNA target) is a single-step LAMP platform using reverse transcriptase enzyme to transcribe RNA targets into cDNA before *Bst* DNA polymerase starts target amplification [5, 6].

2. Multiplex LAMP:

- (i) LEC-LAMP (loop primer endonuclease cleavage) is a modified LAMP to detect multiple targets in one assay reaction [7]. The 5'-end of each forward loop primer for each target sequence is modified with an abasic site flanked by different fluorescent dyes and quenchers. The LEC-LAMP assay is also modified to include endonuclease IV enzyme to help differentiate single-nucleotide polymorphisms [7].

- (ii) MERT-LAMP (multiple endonuclease restriction real-time LAMP assay) is a similar endonuclease-based LAMP where the inner forward primers contain the endonuclease recognition site and are labelled with a fluorophore at the 5' end with a suitable quencher in the middle of the sequence [8, 9].
 - (iii) Melting temperature-dependent LAMP was developed for the simultaneous detection of *Salmonella* and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*. The LAMP assay contained the two primers sets to specifically amplify both bacterial species with a subsequent melting curve analysis to differentiate the detected target sequence. The method required optimization of primers concentrations to ensure the lack of preferential amplification [10].
3. LAMP-on-a-chip (microfluidic-based and paper-based chips) offers a mobile point-of-care innovative LAMP to be used for bedside or pen-side detection combining sample preparation methods with molecular detection [11]. A point-of-care LAMP device was also developed to allow lysis, mixing and LAMP amplification on a microfluidic chip. The system is composed of the chip and a small analyser that is supported with a portable battery and is controlled by a smartphone, allowing the real-time fluorescent signal to be transmitted and displayed on the smartphone [12].
4. Digital/droplet LAMP (single-cell/molecule LAMP) is a recently developed platform mirroring digital PCR and employs single-cell generation techniques with LAMP detection. Droplet LAMP offers detection at a single-molecule level with great potential for multiplex detection [13].

LIMITATIONS

Quantification of target DNA can vary between different LAMP assays; thus it can be particularly challenging to establish diagnostic performance criteria with some sample types. Moreover, differentiation of active infection versus asymptomatic colonization can be difficult, and LAMP does not differentiate between live and dead cells. Therefore, these limitations must be considered when LAMP is employed as a diagnostic tool. A recent study employed sample treatment prior to LAMP detection to differentiate live and dead bacterial cells using propidium monozone, offering a potential solution to one of these limitations. Propidium monozone, after photoactivation, can penetrate compromised and damaged bacterial membranes and bind to the DNA preventing amplification. Thus, it was used as a LAMP pretreatment to detect viable but non-culturable *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* [14]. Designing LAMP primers also tends to present a challenge compared to PCR, due to the requirements for multiple (up to six) long (ca. 40–45-mer) primers [3], with an increased possibility of primer–primer interactions [15]. However, currently available software and web-based applications offer significant assistance in LAMP primer design. Additionally, multiplexing methods are not as well developed for LAMP assays as for other diagnostics, such as PCR, which currently means high-throughput sampling is difficult [7].

Limitations at a glance:

- (1) Quantification is relative and performance criteria can be difficult to establish.
- (2) Does not differentiate between live/dead target cells.
- (3) Primer–primer interactions could affect specificity.
- (4) Multiplexing methods are less developed.

ADVANTAGES

LAMP has many advantages as a diagnostic tool. These include high sensitivity and specificity, with an ability to detect very low copy numbers of nucleic acid in a sample. LAMP assays can be up 1000-fold more sensitive than conventional PCR [16]. Additionally, LAMP is a low-cost diagnostic and, as the method is isothermal, there is no need for expensive thermocyclers to regulate the temperature as with PCR; only a simple heating block is required [4]. Thus, LAMP can easily be employed in field settings, with simple sample preparation methods across a wide variety of samples types (DNA, cultures, faecal material and environmental samples). The assay is also very easy to perform, and, depending on the detection method, requires little or no technical expertise to run the assay or interpret the test results. The LAMP technique has also been demonstrated to be particularly robust and suffering less from biological inhibitors that are known to reduce PCR efficiency [5, 17]; facilitating detection from crude extracts and therefore saving time and resources required for culture and nucleic acid extraction/purification [5].

Advantages at a glance:

- (1) Real-time when coupled with fluorometric detection.
- (2) Sensitive.
- (3) Specific.
- (4) Low cost.
- (5) User-friendly results.
- (6) Mobile/field friendly.
- (7) Can be used with different sample types.

- (8) Less sensitive to PCR inhibitors.
- (9) Can be used in remote or outbreak settings.

RECENT AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

LAMP has undergone many enhancements and has been widely adopted as a diagnostic tool to detect various pathogens, including *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*, *Campylobacter*, *Mycobacterium*, influenza, HIV, etc. [3]. It has also been used to detect parasites such as *Babesia gibsoni* in dogs [18] and African trypanosomes [19], to differentiate dengue virus serotypes [20] and to detect *Streptococcus pneumoniae* virulence factor-encoding gene autolysin (*lytA*) [21]. Another interesting study utilized OmniAmp polymerase, a thermostable viral DNA polymerase that has strand displacement and reverse transcriptase activity, making it suitable for both DNA and RNA targets [22]. The use of OmniAmp polymerase allowed amplification at higher temperatures (66–72 °C), which resulted in 20% faster detection in comparison to *Bst* polymerase [22]. Most recently, LAMP has been applied to detect severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) utilizing a portable device that allows wireless communication of detection data to smartphones [5, 23, 24].

Even though there have been many developments in LAMP assays, there remains a need to further develop molecular modifications to allow robust and easy multiplex detection. Facilitating rapid multiplex detection of multiple pathogens in resource-limited settings or in outbreaks will be an essential tool for the future of diagnostics. The further development of mobile isothermal amplification devices simultaneous with user-friendly universal smartphone detection algorithms that can connect in real-time central laboratories with field studies or hot outbreaks areas will also be key to the success of future molecular detection systems. Lastly, further developments are currently ongoing regarding the development of point-of-care detection and microfluidics designs to facilitate a lab-on-a-chip approach, and to allow this molecular tool to be more effectively and rapidly used in outbreak settings. These developments will be essential for designing cost-effective, rapid and mobile LAMP assays that facilitate the simultaneous detection of multiple pathogens, particularly in resource-limited settings.

OPEN QUESTIONS

- Can LAMP replace traditional culture methodologies?
- How is LAMP sensitivity affected by the different sample types or sample preparation methods?
- What advantages will the digital droplet LAMP have for field or bedside detection?
- Will LAMP become the next diagnostics gold standard after PCR?
- Could LAMP contribute to the fight against antimicrobial resistance (AMR) by helping with the selection of appropriate treatments for infectious diseases?

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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